

Time-Varying Exponentially Fading Memory Signatures

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Abstract. We introduce the *Time-Varying Exponentially Fading Memory* (TV-EFM) signature, denoted by $\text{TVSig}(X; f)^\lambda$. The TV-EFM can be interpreted as a mean-reverting analogue of the classical path signature, with a time-dependent speed of reversion. The recently proposed EFM signature corresponds to the particular case in which the TV-EFM signature becomes stationary. We show that the TV-EFM signature preserves several fundamental algebraic and analytical properties of signatures, including an adapted Chen identity, the linearization property, path determination, and a universal approximation property. In particular, the TV-EFM signature of Brownian motion augmented with time evolves as an inhomogeneous Ornstein–Uhlenbeck process. From a numerical perspective, TV-EFM with a squared function, $\text{TVSig}(X; t^2)^\lambda$, can outperform both the classical signature and the EFM signature in learning inhomogeneous Ornstein–Uhlenbeck dynamics with a periodic mean-reversion speed. Moreover, in a statistical arbitrage framework, we show that the use of the TV-EFM signature yields more precise entry and exit signals.

1. INTRODUCTION

Path signatures and their limitations. The path signature, introduced by Chen [1958] and developed into a powerful analytical and computational tool through the theory of rough paths [Lyons et al., 2007a, Friz and Hairer, 2020], has emerged as a canonical feature map for sequential data. By encoding the geometry of a path X through an infinite collection of iterated integrals, the signature possesses remarkable algebraic structure — including the *Chen identity* and the *shuffle product* — and enjoys a universal approximation property that makes it well-suited for functional regression and machine learning on path spaces. These properties have motivated a growing body of applications in stochastic analysis [Cuchiero et al., 2023, Abi Jaber et al., 2024], time series classification [Chevyrev and Kormilitzin, 2016a, Morrill et al., 2020, Diehl and Reizenstein, 2024], and financial modeling [Abi Jaber and Gérard, 2024]. However, the classical

signature of a path X over a fixed interval $[0, T]$ suffers from a fundamental shortcoming in the context of time-invariant, stationary modeling: its output is *not stationary*. As the time horizon grows, higher-order signature elements dominate, producing explosive behavior analogous to a truncated Taylor expansion applied far from its expansion point. This manifests concretely in overfitting and poor out-of-sample performance when a model trained on $[0, T_1]$ is evaluated on a longer interval $[0, T_2]$ with $T_2 > T_1$ as highlighted in Abi Jaber and Gérard [2024].

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EFM signature as a stationary solution. [Abi Jaber and Sotnikov \[2025\]](#) address this shortcoming by introducing the *Exponentially Fading Memory* (EFM) signature, defined as:

$$\mathbb{X}_t^{\lambda, \mathbf{i}_1 \cdots \mathbf{i}_n} := \int_{-\infty < u_1 < \cdots < u_n < t} e^{-\lambda^{i_1}(t-u_1)} dX_{u_1}^{i_1} \cdots e^{-\lambda^{i_n}(t-u_n)} dX_{u_n}^{i_n}, \quad t \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (1.1)$$

This construction elegantly combines three desiderata: the *time-invariance* of Volterra series [[Boyd and Chua, 1985](#)], the *algebraic tractability* of path signatures, and the *Markovian structure* of the exponential moving average. When applied to time-augmented Brownian motion $\widehat{W}_t = (t, W_t)$, the EFM signature evolves as a group-valued Ornstein–Uhlenbeck process, and its law is stationary, ergodic, and exponentially mixing in the Wasserstein distance.

The need for time-varying memory. Despite these appealing properties, the EFM signature of time-augmented Brownian motion evolves as a group-valued Ornstein–Uhlenbeck process. This is restrictive in many practically relevant settings. Consider for instance:

- **Seasonal financial dynamics**, where the mean-reversion speed of a spread varies with the time of year (e.g., commodity markets, interest rates exhibiting the turn-of-year effect);
- **Inhomogeneous Ornstein–Uhlenbeck processes**, where either the mean level $\theta(t)$ or the reversion speed $\kappa(t)$ is periodic or time-varying;
- **Non-stationary signal processing**, where the relevance of past observations decays at a rate that itself depends on the current regime or time of day.

In all such cases, a fixed exponential weight $e^{-\lambda(t-u)}$ may fail to capture the adaptive, time-dependent obsolescence of historical information. A natural approach is therefore to use the exponential weight $e^{-\lambda \int_u^t f(s) ds}$, where f is integrable and strictly positive.

Contributions. In this paper, we introduce the *Time-Varying Exponentially Fading Memory* (TV-EFM) signature, obtained by replacing the exponent $\lambda(t-u)$ in (1.1) with the integrated weight $\lambda \int_u^t f(s) ds$, for a positive, integrable function $f : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$. Our contributions are as follows.

1. **Algebraic, analytic and stochastic properties.** We establish the main structural properties of TV-EFM, including a modified Chen identity, a linearization property, and a universal approximation theorem for continuous functionals on path space. We further characterize the conditions under which TV-EFM inherits stationarity from the input process. Finally, we derive an Itô decomposition for linear functionals of the TV-EFM of time-augmented Brownian motion.
2. **Numerical experiments.** We evaluate the performance of the TV-EFM signature through three applications.
 - **Simulation of a seasonal OU process.** We consider two particular cases of TV-EFM to simulate an inhomogeneous Ornstein–Uhlenbeck process whose mean level follows a periodic seasonal dynamics of exponential-sinusoidal type.
 - **Ridge regression on an OU process with periodic mean-reversion speed.** We apply ridge regression to an Ornstein–Uhlenbeck process with a periodic mean-reversion speed. The results show that TV-EFM, with a memory decay function $f(t) = t^2$, significantly can outperform both the classical signature and the EFM signature in terms of predictive accuracy.

- **Optimal stopping problem in statistical arbitrage.** We illustrate the usefulness of TV-EFM in a decision-making context by applying it to an optimal stopping problem for stationary processes. This approach yields more precise entry and exit signals.

Related literature. The signature of a path, introduced by [Chen \[1958\]](#), provides a canonical representation of sequential data through iterated integrals and plays a central role in the theory of rough paths developed by Lyons and collaborators [[Lyons et al., 2007a](#), [Friz and Hairer, 2020](#)]. The algebraic and analytical structure of signatures, including Chen’s identity and the shuffle product, makes them particularly suitable as universal feature maps for functions of paths. These properties have led to a growing body of work exploiting signatures in machine learning and time series analysis [[Kidger et al., 2019](#), [Arribas et al., 2018](#), [Fermanian, 2021](#), [Chevyrev and Kormilitzin, 2016a](#), [Levin et al., 2016](#), [Morrill et al., 2020](#), [Diehl and Reizenstein, 2024](#)], as well as in stochastic analysis and financial modeling [[Buehler et al., 2020](#), [Kalsi et al., 2020](#), [Arribas et al., 2020](#), [Lyons et al., 2020](#), [Jaber and Gérard, 2025](#), [Cuchiero et al., 2023](#), [Abi Jaber and Gérard, 2024](#), [Jaber et al., 2025](#), [Futter et al., 2023](#), [Bank et al., 2025](#)]. At the same time, many real-world systems exhibit explicit dependence on past observations, which motivates models with fading or structured memory. In classical systems theory this is captured by Volterra operators and fading memory representations [[Boyd and Chua, 1985](#)], which describe how past inputs influence the present through temporal kernels. Extensions of rough path theory to Volterra-type systems have been investigated in [Harang and Tindel \[2021\]](#). In a related direction, [Hager et al. \[2026\]](#) introduce the *Volterra signature*, a kernel-weighted generalization of the classical signature designed to represent history-dependent systems through iterated Volterra integrals. More recently, [Abi Jaber and Sotnikov \[2025\]](#) introduced the exponentially fading memory (EFM) signature, which incorporates an exponential kernel into the signature representation and yields stationary Markovian dynamics in the tensor algebra.

Outline Section 2 recalls the necessary background on path signatures and the tensor algebra. Section 3 introduces the TV-EFM signature, its operators, dynamics, and key properties. Section 4 develops the algebraic and analytic theory. Section 5 presents numerical experiments.

2. REMINDER ON SIGNATURE

2.1 Algebras of tensors

Signatures take values in a certain graded space : the tensor algebra. We will now define this space and its algebraic structure.

Definition 2.1. Let $d \geq 1$. The (extended) tensor algebra over \mathbb{R}^d is defined as

$$\mathcal{T}(\mathbb{R}^d) := \{a = (a_n)_{n \geq 0} \mid a_n \in (\mathbb{R}^d)^{\otimes n} \text{ for all } n \geq 0\}. \quad (2.1)$$

For a fixed integer $N \in \mathbb{N}$, we introduce the truncated tensor algebra of order N by

$$\mathcal{T}^{(N)}(\mathbb{R}^d) := \{a = (a_n)_{n \geq 0} \in \mathcal{T}(\mathbb{R}^d) \mid a_n = 0 \text{ for all } n \geq N\}.$$

Finally, we define the (non-completed) tensor algebra as

$$\mathcal{T}_f(\mathbb{R}^d) := \bigcup_{N \geq 0} \mathcal{T}^{(N)}(\mathbb{R}^d) \subset \mathcal{T}(\mathbb{R}^d).$$

Algebraic structure. Elements of $\mathcal{T}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ are sequences of tensors indexed by their order. The space $\mathcal{T}_f(\mathbb{R}^d)$ consists precisely of those sequences with finite support, while $\mathcal{T}^{(N)}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ contains tensors of degree strictly less than N . We endow $\mathcal{T}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ with a natural algebraic structure, given $a = (a_n)_{n \geq 0}$ and $b = (b_n)_{n \geq 0}$ in $\mathcal{T}(\mathbb{R}^d)$, their sum is defined componentwise by

$$a + b := (a_n + b_n)_{n \geq 0},$$

whereas their tensor product is given by the Cauchy-type convolution

$$a \otimes b := \left(\sum_{k=0}^n a_k \otimes b_{n-k} \right)_{n \geq 0}.$$

Scalar multiplication by $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ is defined as $\lambda a := (\lambda a_n)_{n \geq 0}$. These operations restrict naturally to $\mathcal{T}_f(\mathbb{R}^d)$ and to each $\mathcal{T}^{(N)}(\mathbb{R}^d)$.

Canonical bases. Let $\{e_1, \dots, e_d\}$ be a fixed basis of \mathbb{R}^d and let $\{e_1^*, \dots, e_d^*\}$ denote its dual basis in $(\mathbb{R}^d)^*$. For each $n \geq 1$, these choices induce canonical bases of the tensor powers $(\mathbb{R}^d)^{\otimes n}$ and $((\mathbb{R}^d)^*)^{\otimes n}$, respectively, given by

$$\{e_{i_1} \otimes \dots \otimes e_{i_n} \mid i_j \in \{1, \dots, d\}\}, \quad \{e_{i_1}^* \otimes \dots \otimes e_{i_n}^* \mid i_j \in \{1, \dots, d\}\}.$$

By collecting these bases across all tensor levels, we obtain canonical bases for $\mathcal{T}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ and its dual space $\mathcal{T}((\mathbb{R}^d)^*)$.

Identification with words. The dual tensor algebra $\mathcal{T}((\mathbb{R}^d)^*)$ can be naturally identified with a space of words. Let

$$\mathcal{A}_d := \{1, 2, \dots, d\}$$

be an alphabet with d symbols, and let $\mathcal{W}(\mathcal{A}_d)$ denote the real vector space generated by all finite words over \mathcal{A}_d . Under this identification, a basis element

$$e_{i_1}^* \otimes \dots \otimes e_{i_n}^*$$

corresponds to the word $i_1 \dots i_n \in \mathcal{W}(\mathcal{A}_d)$.

The empty word will be denoted by $\emptyset \in \mathcal{W}(\mathcal{A}_d)$. With this convention, we obtain the natural identification

$$\mathcal{T}((\mathbb{R}^d)^*) \simeq \mathcal{W}(\mathcal{A}_d).$$

Example 2.2. We illustrate this identification with several examples in dimension $d = 2$. In this case, the alphabet is given by

$$\mathcal{A}_2 = \{1, 2\}.$$

1. Let $a := 2 + e_1 - e_2 \otimes e_1 \in \mathcal{T}((\mathbb{R}^2))$. Then $\langle \emptyset, a \rangle = 2$ and $\langle 21, a \rangle = -1$.
2. Let $a := e_1 \otimes e_2 - e_2 \otimes e_1 \in \mathcal{T}((\mathbb{R}^2))$. Then $\langle 12 + 21, a \rangle = 1 - 1 = 0$.
3. Let $a := -1 + 3e_1^{\otimes 3} \in \mathcal{T}((\mathbb{R}^2))$. Then $\langle 2 \cdot \emptyset + 2 + 111, a \rangle = 2(-1) + 0 + 3 = 1$.

Tensor algebra. The tensor algebra $T((\mathbb{R}^d))$ admits a canonical basis indexed by all words \mathbf{v} over the alphabet \mathcal{A}_d . Consequently, any element $\ell \in T((\mathbb{R}^d))$ can be written as

$$\ell = \sum_{n \geq 0} \sum_{|\mathbf{v}|=n} \ell^{\mathbf{v}} \mathbf{v},$$

where $\ell^{\mathbf{v}} \in \mathbb{R}$ denotes the coefficient associated with the word \mathbf{v} .

Some useful function spaces: For $n > 1$ we define the simplex

$$\Delta_n(a, b) := \{(t_0, \dots, t_n) : a = t_0 \leq \dots \leq t_n \leq b\}$$

2.2 The signature transform

Definition 2.3 (classical signature). Let $S : [0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ be a smooth path. The signature of S is defined as the map

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Sig}^\infty : [0, T]^2 &\longrightarrow T((\mathbb{R}^d)), \\ (s, t) &\longmapsto \text{Sig}_{s,t}^\infty := (1, \text{Sig}_{s,t}^1, \dots, \text{Sig}_{s,t}^n, \dots). \end{aligned}$$

where, for each $n \geq 1$,

$$\text{Sig}_{s,t}^n := \int_{\Delta_n(s,t)} dS_{u_1} \otimes \dots \otimes dS_{u_n} \in (\mathbb{R}^d)^{\otimes n}.$$

For a fixed order $N \in \mathbb{N}$, the truncated signature is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Sig}^{\leq N} : [0, T]^2 &\longrightarrow T^{(N)}(\mathbb{R}^d), \\ (s, t) &\longmapsto \text{Sig}_{s,t}^{\leq N} := (1, \text{Sig}_{s,t}^1, \dots, \text{Sig}_{s,t}^N). \end{aligned}$$

Whenever the interval $[s, t]$ is omitted, the notation Sig^∞ refers implicitly to $\text{Sig}_{0,T}^\infty$.

Example 2.4. Let $S_t = (S_t^1, S_t^2)$ be a continuous semimartingale in \mathbb{R}^2 . Using the word notation introduced previously, the following identities hold:

1.

$$\langle \emptyset, \text{Sig}_{0,t}^\infty \rangle = 1.$$

2.

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathbf{1}, \text{Sig}_{0,t}^\infty \rangle &= \int_0^t \circ dS_s^1 \\ &= S_t^1 - S_0^1. \end{aligned}$$

3.

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathbf{22}, \text{Sig}_{0,t}^\infty \rangle &= \int_0^t \int_0^s \circ dS_u^2 \circ dS_s^2 \\ &= \frac{1}{2} (S_t^2 - S_0^2)^2. \end{aligned}$$

4.

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \mathbf{12}, \text{Sig}_{0,t}^\infty \rangle &= \int_0^t \int_0^s \circ dS_u^1 \circ dS_s^2 \\ &= \int_0^t (S_s^1 - S_0^1) \circ dS_s^2. \end{aligned}$$

5. Let $\ell \in T((\mathbb{R}^2)^*)$. Then

$$\langle \ell \mathbf{1}, \text{Sig}_{0,t}^\infty \rangle = \int_0^t \langle \ell, \text{Sig}_{0,s}^\infty \rangle \circ dS_s^1.$$

3. TIME-VARYING EXPONENTIALLY FADING MEMORY SIGNATURE

In what follows, $f \in L^1([0, T])$ denotes a strictly positive function. To lighten notation, we set

$$F_{s,t} := \int_s^t f(u) du, \quad (3.1)$$

the cumulative functional of f over the interval $[s, t]$.

Definition 3.1. Let $d, n \in \mathbb{N}$. Consider a parameter vector $\lambda = (\lambda^1, \dots, \lambda^d) \in (\mathbb{R}_+^*)^d$ with strictly positive components, and let $X = (X^1, \dots, X^d)$ be a continuous \mathbb{R}^d -valued semimartingale defined on the interval $[s, t]$, where $s < t$.

Time-Varying Exponentially Fading Memory (TV-EFM) signature of X over $[s, t]$ is denoted by

$$\text{TVSig}(X; f)^\lambda_{s,t} := (1, \text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s,t}^{1;\lambda}, \text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s,t}^{2;\lambda}, \dots) \in \widetilde{T}(\mathbb{R}^d),$$

where $\widetilde{T}(\mathbb{R}^d)$ is as defined in (2.1).

For $n \geq 1$, the n -th level of the signature is given by the iterated Stratonovich integrals

$$\text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s,t}^{n;\lambda} := \int_{\Delta_n(s,t)} (e^{-\lambda F_{u_1,t}} \odot dX_{u_1}) \otimes \dots \otimes \circ(e^{-\lambda F_{u_n,t}} \odot dX_{u_n}), \quad (3.2)$$

where \odot denotes the Hadamard (component-wise) product.

More explicitly, for a multi-index $\mathbf{I} = \mathbf{i}_1 \cdots \mathbf{i}_k \in \{1, \dots, d\}^k$, the corresponding component is given by

$$\text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s,t}^{\mathbf{i}_1 \cdots \mathbf{i}_k; \lambda} = \int_{\Delta_k(s,t)} e^{-\lambda^{i_1} F_{u_1,t}} dX_{u_1}^{i_1} \dots e^{-\lambda^{i_k} F_{u_k,t}} dX_{u_k}^{i_k}.$$

This definition admits a natural recursive formulation. For any multi-index $I = (i_1, \dots, i_k)$, one has

$$\text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s,t}^{\mathbf{i}_1 \cdots \mathbf{i}_k; \lambda} = \int_s^t e^{-\lambda^{i_1 \cdots i_k} F_{u,t}} \text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s,u}^{\mathbf{i}_1 \cdots \mathbf{i}_{k-1}; \lambda} dX_u^{i_k}. \quad (3.3)$$

where

$$\lambda^{\mathbf{i}_1 \cdots \mathbf{i}_n} := \sum_{k=1}^n \lambda^{i_k}. \quad (3.4)$$

Example 3.2. For a one-dimensional process X_t with $d = 1$ and $f(x) = 1$, the TV-EFM signature corresponds to the Exponentially Fading Memory signature defined by Eduardo and Dimitri in (1.1).

$$\text{TVSig}(X; 1)_{s,t}^\lambda = \left(1, (U_t - U_s), \frac{(U_t - U_s)^2}{2!}, \dots, \frac{(U_t - U_s)^n}{n!}, \dots \right),$$

where

$$U_t^\lambda := \int_{-\infty}^t e^{-\lambda(t-u)} dX_u.$$

Example 3.3. For $d = 2$ and $f(t) = t$ for $n = 1, 2$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{TVSig}(X; t)_{s,t}^{0;\lambda} &= 1, & \text{TVSig}(X; t)_{s,t}^{1;\lambda} &= \begin{pmatrix} U_t^{\lambda^1} \\ U_t^{\lambda^2} \end{pmatrix}, \\ \text{TVSig}(X; t)_{s,t}^{2;\lambda} &= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{(U_t^{\lambda^1})^2}{2!} & \int_s^t e^{-(\lambda^1 + \lambda^2)F_{u,t}} U_u^{\lambda^1} \circ dX_u^2 \\ \int_s^t e^{-(\lambda^1 + \lambda^2)F_{u,t}} U_u^{\lambda^2} \circ dX_u^1 & \frac{(U_t^{\lambda^2})^2}{2!} \end{pmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

where

$$U_t^{\lambda^i} := \int_0^t e^{-\lambda^i F_{u,t}} dX_u, \quad F_{u,t} = \frac{t^2 - u^2}{2}$$

3.1 Time-Varying Exponentially Fading Memory Signature dynamics

We begin by introducing two linear operators that play a central role in the analysis of Time-Varying Exponentially Fading Memory signatures (TV-EFM) and in the study of their dynamical properties.

Definition 3.4. We define the linear operator

$$\Lambda_{f(t)} : T((\mathbb{R}^d)) \longrightarrow T((\mathbb{R}^d))$$

as follows. For any element

$$\ell = \sum_{n \geq 0} \sum_{|\mathbf{v}|=n} \ell^{\mathbf{v}},$$

we set

$$\Lambda_{f(t)}(\ell) := \sum_{n \geq 0} \sum_{|\mathbf{v}|=n} f(t) \lambda^{\mathbf{v}} \ell^{\mathbf{v}}. \quad (3.5)$$

where $\lambda^{\mathbf{v}}$ is as defined in (3.4).

Definition 3.5. Let $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^d$, let $t = (t_1, t_2)$. We define the *exponential weighting operator*

$$\Phi_t^{\lambda, f} : T((\mathbb{R}^d)) \longrightarrow T((\mathbb{R}^d))$$

by

$$\Phi_t^{\lambda, f}(\ell) := \sum_{n \geq 0} \sum_{|\mathbf{v}|=n} e^{-\lambda^{\mathbf{v}} F_{t_1, t_2}} \ell^{\mathbf{v}}. \quad (3.6)$$

Proposition 3.6. The following properties hold. Let $t = (t_1, t_2)$.

1. The operator $\Phi_t^{\lambda, f}$ is a dilation operator: it multiplies the i -th basis vector by

$$e^{-\lambda^i F_{t_1, t_2}}.$$

2. For any $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \in \mathbb{R}^d$, we have the semigroup property

$$\Phi_t^{\lambda_1, f} \Phi_t^{\lambda_2, f} = \Phi_t^{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2, f}.$$

3. For all $t_1 \leq t_2 \leq t_3$,

$$\Phi_{t_1, t_2}^{\lambda, f} \Phi_{t_2, t_3}^{\lambda, f} = \Phi_{t_1, t_3}^{\lambda, f}.$$

4. Denoting by $t_i \in \mathbb{R}$ the i -th component of t , we have

$$\frac{d}{dt_i} \Phi_t^{\lambda, f} = -\Lambda_{f(t_i)} \Phi_t^{\lambda, f}.$$

5. For any $p, q \in T((\mathbb{R}^d))$, the operator $\Phi_t^{\lambda, f}$ is multiplicative with respect to the tensor product:

$$\Phi_t^{\lambda, f}(p \otimes q) = (\Phi_t^{\lambda, f} p) \otimes (\Phi_t^{\lambda, f} q).$$

6. For any $p, q \in T((\mathbb{R}^d))$, the operator Λ_{f, t_i} satisfies the Leibniz rule

$$\Lambda_{f(t_i)}(p \otimes q) = (\Lambda_{f(t_i)} p) \otimes q + p \otimes (\Lambda_{f(t_i)} q).$$

Proof. See 6

□

Proposition 3.6 and 3.5 allows us to rewrite the **Time-Varying Exponentially Fading Memory Signature** as

$$\text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s, t}^\lambda = \int_s^t \Phi_{u, t}^{\lambda, f} (\text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s, u}^\lambda \otimes dX_u). \quad (3.7)$$

Proposition 3.7. Fix $s > 0$. Suppose that $\sigma = (\sigma_t)_{t \geq s}$ is a continuous $T((\mathbb{R}^d))$ -valued semimartingale such that

$$\int_s^t e^{-2\lambda v F_{s, u}} d\langle \sigma^v \rangle_u < \infty$$

for all words v and $t \geq s$. Then, for all $\ell_s \in T((\mathbb{R}^d))$, the process

$$\ell_t = \Phi_{t, s}^{\lambda, f} \ell_s + \int_s^t \Phi_{t, u}^{\lambda, f} d\sigma_u$$

solves the equation

$$d\ell_t = -\Lambda_{f(t)} \ell_t dt + d\sigma_t.$$

Proof. The proof follows immediately from Proposition 3.6 (4)

□

Using Proposition 3.7, we can show that the TV-EFM signature satisfies the following differential equation:

$$d(\text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s, t}^\lambda) = -\Lambda_{f(t)} \text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s, t}^\lambda dt + \text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s, t}^\lambda \otimes \circ dX_t \quad (3.8)$$

Proposition 3.8. Fix $x \in T(\mathbb{R}^d)$. The solution to the equation

$$\begin{cases} d\Psi_t^{s,x} = -\Lambda_{f(t)} \Psi_t^{s,x} dt + \Psi_t^{s,x} \otimes \circ dX_t, & t \geq s, \\ \Psi_s^{s,x} = x, \end{cases}$$

is given by

$$\Psi_t^{s,x} = \Phi_{s,t}^{\lambda,f}(x) \otimes \text{TVSig}(x; f)_{s,t}^\lambda \quad (3.9)$$

Proof. The proof follows that of Proposition 3.7 in [Abi Jaber and Sotnikov \[2025\]](#), with the operator \mathbf{D} replaced by our semigroup operator Φ . \square

Remark 3.9. When f is constant, we recover all the properties of the EFM signature described in [Abi Jaber and Sotnikov \[2025\]](#).

3.2 Well-definedness of the Time-Varying Exponentially Fading Memory Signatures and its fading-memory properties

We now establish the conditions ensuring that the Time-Varying Exponentially Fading Memory signature from Definition 3.1 is well-defined for continuous semimartingales.

Proposition 3.10 (Well-definedness and continuity of the Time-Varying Exponentially Fading Memory Signatures on a finite interval). Let $T > 0$, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}_+^d$, and $f \in L^1([0, T])$. Let $X : [0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ be an absolutely continuous path with finite weighted variation

$$\|X\|_{\text{BV}, \lambda, f} < \infty.$$

$$\|X\|_{\text{BV}, \lambda, f; [s, t]} := \int_s^t \left| \Phi_{u, t}^{\lambda, f} \dot{X}_u \right| du, \quad \|X\|_{\text{BV}, \lambda, f} := \|X\|_{\text{BV}, \lambda, f; (-\infty, T]}.$$

Then for every $0 \leq s \leq t \leq T$ and every $n \geq 1$, the n -th level of the TV-EFM signature $\text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s, t}^{\mathbf{n}; \lambda}$ is well-defined and satisfies the estimate

$$\|\text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s, t}^{\mathbf{n}; \lambda}\| \leq \frac{\|X\|_{\text{BV}, \lambda, f; [s, t]}^n}{n!}. \quad (3.10)$$

Proposition 3.11 (Rough convolution integral with the exponential operator $\Phi^{\lambda, f}$). Let $T > 0$ and let $\mathbf{X} = (X, \mathbb{X}) \in C^\gamma([0, T], \mathbb{R}^d)$ for some $\gamma \in (1/3, 1/2]$. Let $\Phi_{u, t}^{\lambda, f}$ be the exponential weighting operator defined in 3.5, satisfying the two-parameter semigroup property and multiplicativity with respect to the tensor product.

Assume that $(Y, Y') \in \mathcal{D}_{\Phi^{\lambda, f}, \mathbf{X}}^{2\gamma}([0, T], \mathcal{H}_\alpha^d)$, i.e.

$$R_{t, s}^Y := \delta Y_{t, s} - \Phi_{s, t}^{\lambda, f}(Y'_s X_{t, s}) \in C^{2\gamma}([0, T]; \mathcal{H}_\alpha).$$

Then the integral defined by

$$\int_s^t \Phi_{u, t}^{\lambda, f}(Y_u dX_u) := \lim_{|P| \rightarrow 0} \sum_{[u, v] \in P} \Phi_{u, t}^{\lambda, f}(Y_u X_{v, u} + Y'_u \mathbb{X}_{v, u}) \quad (3.11)$$

exists as an element of $\widehat{C}^\gamma \mathcal{H}_\alpha$ and satisfies, for every $0 \leq \beta < 3\gamma$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\| \int_s^t \Phi_{u,t}^{\lambda,f}(Y_u dX_u) - \Phi_{s,t}^{\lambda,f}(Y_s)X_{t,s} - \Phi_{s,t}^{\lambda,f}(Y'_s)\mathbb{X}_{t,s} \right\|_{\mathcal{H}_{\alpha+\beta}} \\ & \lesssim \left(\|R^Y\|_{2\gamma,\alpha} \|X\|_\gamma + \|Y'\|_{\gamma,\alpha} \|\mathbb{X}\|_{2\gamma} \right) |t-s|^{3\gamma-\beta}. \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, the map

$$(Y, Y') \mapsto (Z, Z') := \left(\int_0^\cdot \Phi_{u,\cdot}^{\lambda,f}(Y_u dX_u), Y \right)$$

is continuous from $\mathcal{D}_{\Phi^{\lambda,f}, \mathbf{X}}^{2\gamma}([0, T], \mathcal{H}_\alpha^d)$ to $\mathcal{D}_{\Phi^{\lambda,f}, \mathbf{X}}^{2\gamma}([0, T], \mathcal{H}_\alpha)$ and one has the bound

$$\|Z, Z'\|_{\mathbf{X}, 2\gamma, \alpha} \lesssim \|Y\|_{\gamma, \alpha} + \left(\|Y'_0\|_{\mathcal{H}_\alpha} + \|(Y, Y')\|_{\mathbf{X}, 2\gamma, \alpha} \right) (\|X\|_\gamma + \|\mathbb{X}\|_{2\gamma}).$$

Proof. The proof follows verbatim the argument of [Gerasimovičs and Hairer, 2018, Theorem 3.5], with the sole modification that the semigroup S_{t-s} is replaced by the exponential weighting operator $\Phi_{s,t}^{\lambda,f}$. Since $\Phi_{s,t}^{\lambda,f}$ satisfies the same structural properties required in the proof, namely the two-parameter semigroup property and multiplicativity with respect to the tensor product, the sewing argument carries over without any further changes. We therefore omit the details. \square

Theorem 3.12. Fix $T \in \mathbb{R}$. If $\mathbf{X} \in \mathcal{C}^{\alpha, \rho}((-\infty, T])$ for some $\alpha \in (\frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2})$ and $\mathbf{0} \prec \boldsymbol{\rho} \prec \boldsymbol{\lambda}$, then the TV-EFM signature $\text{TVSig}(X; f)$ given by (3.2) is well-defined. Moreover, for all $s \in (-\infty, T]$ and all $n \geq 0$, we have

$$\text{TVSig}(\mathbf{X}; f)_{s,\cdot}^n \in \widehat{\mathcal{C}}_b^{\alpha, \rho}((s, T]).$$

Here, $\mathcal{C}^{\alpha, \rho}((-\infty, T])$ denotes the space of functions f defined as in [Abi Jaber and Sotnikov 2025], with our semigroup operator Φ replacing the operator D .

$\boldsymbol{\rho}, \boldsymbol{\lambda} \in \mathbb{R}^d$

Proof. (3.2) and (3.2), The proof follows essentially the same steps as that of Proposition 3.9 and Theorem 3.13 in the paper by [Abi Jaber and Sotnikov 2025]. The only difference lies in the use of our new semigroup operator Φ . \square

3.3 Time-Varying Exponentially Fading Memory Signatures as a stationary process

In this subsection, we show that if X is a process with stationary increments, $\lambda > 0$ and f is constant, then its TV-EFM signature is itself a stationary process. More precisely, for all $t_1 < \dots < t_n$ and for all $h \in \mathbb{R}$, we have

$$\mathcal{L}(\text{TVSig}(X; f)_{t_1}^\lambda, \dots, \text{TVSig}(X; f)_{t_n}^\lambda) = \mathcal{L}(\text{TVSig}(X; f)_{t_1+h}^\lambda, \dots, \text{TVSig}(X; f)_{t_n+h}^\lambda),$$

where \mathcal{L} denotes the law.

Lemma 3.13. *Abi Jaber and Sotnikov [2025]* Let η_t and σ_t be stationary càdlàg adapted processes (possibly multivariate), such that, for all $h \in \mathbb{R}$,

$$\mathcal{L}((\eta_t, \sigma_t, X_t)_{t \in \mathbb{R}}) = \mathcal{L}((\eta_{t+h}, \sigma_{t+h}, X_t^h)_{t \in \mathbb{R}}),$$

where $X_t^h := X_{t+h} - X_h$. Then, for all $\mu > 0$ and $i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$,

$$Y_t = \int_{-\infty}^t e^{-\mu K(t-s)} \sigma_s \circ dX_s^i$$

is stationary and

$$\mathcal{L}((\eta_t, Y_t, X_t)_{t \in \mathbb{R}}) = \mathcal{L}((\eta_{t+h}, Y_{t+h}, X_t^h)_{t \in \mathbb{R}}). \quad (3.12)$$

Proof. The argument is obtained by adapting the proof of [Sauri, 2017, Proposition 1]. The necessary modifications are minor: we work with a semimartingale having stationary increments in place of Brownian motion, we consider the Stratonovich integral instead of the Itô integral, and we include identity (3.12), which follows by the same reasoning as in the cited reference. We therefore omit the details. \square

Theorem 3.14. Let $X = (X_t)_{t \in \mathbb{R}}$ be a continuous \mathbb{R}^d -valued semimartingale with stationary increments. Then the TV-EFM signature is stationary if and only if the memory decay function f is constant. In other words,

$$\mathcal{L}(\text{TVSig}(X; f)_t^\lambda) = \mathcal{L}(\text{TVSig}(X; f)_{t_0}^\lambda) \quad \text{for all } t, t_0 \in \mathbb{R}$$

is equivalent to the existence of a constant $c \geq 0$ such that $f(t) = c$ for all $t \in \mathbb{R}$.

Proof. See 7 \square

4. TIME-VARYING EXPONENTIALLY FADING MEMORY SIGNATURE AND THEIR PROPERTIES

4.1 Chen's identity.

We recall the classical identity due to Chen ?, which plays a fundamental role in the theory of signatures. Let $x \in C_p([a, b], V)$ and $y \in C_p([b, c], V)$ be two paths of finite p -variation. There exists a natural binary operation allowing one to concatenate these two paths into a single path defined on $[a, c]$. The *concatenation* of x and y , denoted by $x * y$, is the path in $C_p([a, c], V)$ defined by

$$(x * y)_t := \begin{cases} x_t, & \text{if } t \in [a, b], \\ y_t - y_b + x_b, & \text{if } t \in [b, c]. \end{cases}$$

A key property of the signature is its compatibility with concatenation. More precisely, the signature of the concatenated path can be expressed solely in terms of the signatures of the individual paths. Indeed, one has

$$\text{Sig}(x * y) = \text{Sig}(x) \otimes \text{Sig}(y),$$

where \otimes denotes the tensor product in the tensor algebra. This fundamental multiplicative property, commonly referred to as *Chen's relation*, is stated formally in the following lemma.

Lemma 4.1 (Chen's relation). Let $1 \leq p < 2$. Assume that $x \in C_p([a, b], V)$ and $y \in C_p([b, c], V)$. Then the signature of the concatenated path $x * y$ over $[a, c]$ satisfies

$$\text{Sig}(x * y)_{[a,c]} = \text{Sig}(x)_{[a,b]} \otimes \text{Sig}(y)_{[b,c]}.$$

Proposition 4.2 (Modified Generalised Chen's relation). Fix $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}_+^d$ and let $X = (X_t)_{t \in \mathbb{R}}$ be a continuous \mathbb{R}^d -valued semimartingale such that the **TV-EFM** signature $\text{TVSig}(X; f)^\lambda$ is well defined. Then, for all $s \leq u \leq t$, one has

$$\text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s,t}^\lambda = (\Phi_{u,t}^{\lambda, f} \text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s,u}^\lambda) \otimes \text{TVSig}(X; f)_{u,t}^\lambda \quad (4.1)$$

Proof. See 8 □

4.2 TV-EFM signature of a linear path

Linear path. Let the path $x : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^d$ is linear, that is,

$$x_t = x_a + \frac{t-a}{b-a} (x_b - x_a), \quad t \in [a, b].$$

Explicit computation of the signature. Suppose that $\lambda = (\lambda, \dots, \lambda)$ for some $\lambda > 0$. Substituting into the definition yields

$$\text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s,t}^\lambda = \exp^{\otimes} \left(\frac{x_t - x_s}{t-s} \int_s^t e^{-\lambda F_{u_1, t}} du_1 \right)$$

where

$$e^{\otimes \ell} := \sum_{k \geq 0} \frac{\ell^{\otimes k}}{k!}.$$

Moreover, the **TV-EFM** signature of a piecewise-linear path with breakpoints $t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_n$ is given recursively by

$$\text{TVSig}(X; f)_{t_0, t_n}^\lambda = \left(\Phi_{t_{n-1}, t_n}^{\lambda, f} \text{TVSig}(X; f)_{t_0, t_{n-1}}^\lambda \right) \otimes \exp^{\otimes} \left(\frac{x_{t_n} - x_{t_{n-1}}}{t_n - t_{n-1}} \int_{t_{n-1}}^{t_n} e^{-\lambda F_{u_1, t_n}} du_1 \right) \quad (4.2)$$

Proof. See 9 □

4.3 Time reparameterization

We now discuss the behavior of the **TV-EFM** signature under time reparameterization. Let $\psi : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a smooth increasing bijection. Given a path X and a function f , define the reparametrized objects

$$\tilde{X}_t := X_{\psi_t}, \quad \tilde{F}_{s,t} := F_{\psi_s, \psi_t}.$$

The n -th level of the **TV-EFM** signature over $[s, t]$ is given in (3.2). For every smooth increasing bijection ψ , one has

$$\text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s,t}^\lambda = \text{TVSig}(\tilde{X}; \tilde{f})_{s,t}^\lambda \quad (4.3)$$

In other words, the **TV-EFM** signature is invariant under simultaneous time reparameterization.

4.4 Linearization property

An important algebraic structure on the tensor algebra $T(\mathbb{R}^{d+1})$ is the shuffle product, which allows one to linearize products of linear functionals of the signature see [Lyons et al., 2007b, Theorem 2.15].

Let $\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w} \in T(\mathbb{R}^{d+1})$, The shuffle product \sqcup is defined recursively by

$$(\mathbf{vi}) \sqcup (\mathbf{wj}) = (\mathbf{v} \sqcup (\mathbf{wj})) \mathbf{i} + ((\mathbf{vi}) \sqcup \mathbf{w}) \mathbf{j},$$

with unit element given by

$$\mathbf{w} \sqcup \emptyset = \emptyset \sqcup \mathbf{w} = \mathbf{w},$$

where \emptyset denotes the empty word.

Proposition 4.3. More precisely, for any two words I, J , one has

$$\langle I \sqcup J, \text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s,t}^\lambda \rangle = \langle I, \text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s,t}^\lambda \rangle \langle J, \text{TVSig}(X; f)_{s,t}^\lambda \rangle. \quad (4.4)$$

Proof. See 10 □

4.5 Universal approximation theorem

Theorem 4.4. Let $K \subset \mathcal{C}^{\alpha, \rho}([0, T], \mathbb{R}^d)$ be a compact set and let

$$H : \mathcal{C}^{\alpha, \rho}([0, T], \mathbb{R}^d) \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

be a continuous function. Then, for any $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $\ell \in T(\mathbb{R}^{d+1})$ such that, for all $X \in K$,

$$|H(X) - \langle \ell, \text{TVSig}(X; f)_{0,T}^\lambda \rangle| < \varepsilon. \quad (4.5)$$

Proof. This theorem can be proved in the same way as [Abi Jaber and Sotnikov \[2025\]](#) Theorem 4.9. □

4.6 Itô's decomposition

We begin this subsection by fixing a general continuous \mathbb{R}^d -valued semimartingale X . The next definition will play a key role in deriving the semimartingale decomposition of linear functionals of its **TV-EFM** signature.

Definition 4.5. Let $\ell \in T((\mathbb{R}^d))$ be a tensor sequence and let \mathbf{u} be a word. The projection $\ell_{\mathbf{u}}$ is defined by

$$\ell_{\mathbf{u}} = \sum_{n \geq 0} \sum_{\mathbf{v} \in V_n} \ell^{\mathbf{vu}} \mathbf{v}. \quad (4.6)$$

In other words, this projection keeps only the coefficients of ℓ corresponding to words that end with \mathbf{u} , and replaces each such word \mathbf{vu} by its prefix \mathbf{v} . The link between this projection and differentiation becomes clear through the following decomposition:

$$\langle \ell, \text{TVSig}(X; f)_t^\lambda \rangle = \langle \ell^\emptyset, \text{TVSig}(X; f)_t^\lambda \rangle + \sum_{i=1}^d \int_0^t \langle \ell_i, \text{TVSig}(X; f)_s^\lambda \rangle \circ dX_s^i. \quad (4.7)$$

Equivalently, in terms of tensor sequences,

$$\ell = \ell^\emptyset + \sum_{i=1}^d \ell_i \mathbf{i}. \quad (4.8)$$

This decomposition yields the Itô formula for (possibly infinite) linear functionals of the signature of semimartingales. In the case of **TV-EFM** signatures, an analogous result holds, the only difference being the presence of exponential weights in the definition, which generates an additional mean-reverting term.

Proposition 4.6. Let $\ell_t \in T(\mathbb{R}^{d+1})$ be continuously differentiable (element-wise). Then the linear functional $\langle \ell_t, \text{TVSig}(X; f)_t^\lambda \rangle$ satisfies the stochastic differential equation

$$d\langle \ell_t, \text{TVSig}(X; f)_t^\lambda \rangle = \langle \dot{\ell}_t - \Lambda_{f,t} \ell_t, \text{TVSig}(X; f)_t^\lambda \rangle dt + \sum_{i=0}^d \langle \ell_{t\mathbf{i}}, \text{TVSig}(X; f)_t^\lambda \rangle \circ dX_t^i. \quad (4.9)$$

Proof. See 10 □

This proposition allows us to derive the Itô formula for the TV-EFM signature $\widehat{\mathbf{W}}_t^\lambda$ of the extended standard Brownian motion $\widehat{W}_t = (t, W_t^1, \dots, W_t^d)$.

Proposition 4.7. Let $\ell_t \in T(\mathbb{R}^{d+1})$ be continuously differentiable (element-wise). Then the process $\langle \ell_t, \text{TVSig}(\widehat{\mathbf{W}}; f)_t^\lambda \rangle$ satisfies

$$d\langle \ell_t, \text{TVSig}(\widehat{\mathbf{W}}; f)_t^\lambda \rangle = \left\langle \dot{\ell}_t - \Lambda_{f,t} \ell_t + \ell_{t\mathbf{0}} + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^d \ell_{t\mathbf{ii}}, \text{TVSig}(\widehat{\mathbf{W}}; f)_t^\lambda \right\rangle dt + \sum_{i=1}^d \langle \ell_{t\mathbf{i}}, \text{TVSig}(\widehat{\mathbf{W}}; f)_t^\lambda \rangle dW_t^i. \quad (4.10)$$

Proof. See 11 □

5. NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTS WITH TV-EFM

5.1 Inhomogeneous Ornstein–Uhlenbeck Process

In this section, we present numerical experiments conducted on simulated data to illustrate the performance of the *Time-Varying Exponentially Fading Memory* (TV-EFM) signature. First, we study the simulation of inhomogeneous Ornstein–Uhlenbeck (OU) processes exhibiting a seasonal component. We simulate these processes using the classical signature and the EFM signature. Second, we use the TV-EFM signature in a statistical learning framework to estimate the dynamics of an inhomogeneous OU process. We then compare the performance obtained for three cases: (i) the classical signature, (ii) the EFM signature, and (iii) TV-EFM with $f(t) = t^2$.

Let:

- **Sig $_{\lambda}$** ($f_{\lambda}(t) = 1$): this corresponds to the **EFM** signature when the kernel is $K(t, s) = \exp(-\lambda(t - s))$.
- **TVSig $_{f_{\lambda}}$** ($f_{\lambda}(t) = t^2$): in real-world applications the kernel is often not explicitly known, but it may still be beneficial to incorporate a kernel weighting the history of the path. In this case the kernel is $K_f(t, s) = \exp(-\lambda F_{s,t})$.

OU with seasonal mean. We consider an OU process whose mean level varies over time, defined by

$$dX_t = (\theta(t) - b_2 X_t)dt + \sigma dW_t, \quad (5.1)$$

where W_t is a standard Brownian motion and $b_2 > 0$ represents the mean-reversion speed. The function $\theta(t)$ introduces a seasonal component into the drift of the process. We consider two commonly used forms of seasonality [Schneider and Tavin \[2018\]](#).

(i) Sinusoidal pattern For $a \geq b > 0$ and $t_0 \in [0, 1[$, the function is defined by

$$\theta^{SP}(t) = a + b \cos(\omega(t - t_0)). \quad (5.2)$$

This specification describes a periodic oscillation around the mean level a , with amplitude b and frequency ω .

(ii) Exponential–sinusoidal pattern For $a, b > 0$ and $t_0 \in [0, 1[$, using the Taylor expansion we obtain

$$\theta_N^{ES}(t) = a \exp(b \cos(\omega(t - t_0))) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{a_m b^m}{m!} \cos^m(\omega(t - t_0)). \quad (5.3)$$

This formulation allows for stronger seasonal variations while ensuring the positivity of the seasonal function. It is notably used in the modeling of certain commodity markets.

OU with seasonal mean-reversion speed. The second model considers a different dynamics in which the mean-reversion speed varies periodically over time, defined in [Jha \[2025\]](#) by

$$dX_t = [\kappa_0 + A \sin(\omega t)](\theta - X_t)dt + \sigma dW_t. \quad (5.4)$$

In this case, the long-term mean level θ remains constant, but the speed of reversion toward this mean is modulated by a periodic component. The parameter κ_0 represents the average mean-reversion speed, while A controls the amplitude of the seasonal variation.

These two types of inhomogeneous OU processes will be used in the remainder of this section to illustrate the two applications studied: trajectory simulation and learning the dynamics of the process using the TVSig signature.

5.1.1 Simulation of the Exponential–Sinusoidal Pattern

Let $X(t)$ be a process defined by

$$dX(t) = \left(\sum_{m=0}^Q \frac{a_m b^m}{m!} \cos^m(\omega t) - b_2 X(t) \right) dt + \sigma dW_t. \quad (5.5)$$

To approximate the seasonal component, we introduce the following function

$$\delta_{b,Q}(x) = \sum_{m=0}^Q \frac{b^m}{m!} \sum_{k=0}^m \binom{m}{k} x_{k,m}.$$

Signature representation (Sig): The solution is given by,

$$X(t) = \langle \ell_{\text{ES}}, \text{Sig}(X)_{0,t} \rangle$$

where

$$\ell_{\text{ES}} = x_0 e^{\llbracket -b_2 \mathbf{1} \rrbracket} + \delta_b(\Re((b_2 - i\nu\omega)e^{\llbracket i\nu\omega \mathbf{1} \rrbracket})) - \delta_b(e^{\llbracket -b_2 \mathbf{1} \rrbracket}) + \sigma \mathbf{2} e^{\llbracket -b_2 \mathbf{1} \rrbracket} \quad (5.6)$$

and where ν is defined by $\nu = m - 2k$.

Case $Q = 0$ In this particular case, the seasonal term reduces to a constant. The process then corresponds to the *standard Ornstein–Uhlenbeck process* with constant drift. The explicit solution of the process is

$$X(t) = \langle \ell_{\text{OU}}, \text{Sig}(X)_{0,t} \rangle$$

where

$$\ell_{\text{OU}} = x_0 e^{\llbracket -b_2 \mathbf{1} \rrbracket} + \frac{a_0}{b_2} (\emptyset - e^{\llbracket -b_2 \mathbf{1} \rrbracket}) + \sigma \mathbf{2} e^{\llbracket -b_2 \mathbf{1} \rrbracket}$$

Case $Q = 1$ The model introduces a *sinusoidal seasonal pattern* in the drift dynamics. The process $X(t)$ then satisfies

$$dX(t) = (\theta^{SP}(t) - b_2 X(t)) dt + \sigma dW_t = (a_0 + a_1 b_1 \cos(\omega t) - b_2 X(t)) dt + \sigma dW_t.$$

The solution of the process is $X(t) = \langle \ell_{\text{SS}}, \text{Sig}(X)_{0,t} \rangle$, where the associated kernel is given by

$$\ell_{\text{SS}} = \left[\left(x - \frac{a_1 b_1}{b_2^2 + \omega^2} \right) \emptyset + a_0 \mathbf{1} - \sigma \mathbf{2} \right] e^{\llbracket -b_2 \mathbf{1} \rrbracket} + \frac{a_1 b_1}{b_2^2 + \omega^2} \Re((b_2 - i\omega) e^{\llbracket i\omega \mathbf{1} \rrbracket})$$

EFM representation (Sig_λ):

For $Q = 1$, The solution is given by, $X(t) = \langle \ell_t^\lambda, \text{Sig}_\lambda \rangle$

$$\ell_t^\lambda = x_0(1 + a \mathbf{1}) - \mu_1 \mathbf{1} + \sigma \mathbf{2} + \frac{\mu_2 \sqrt{2} (a \cos(2\pi t) - a(1 + a \mathbf{1})) + 2\pi \sin(2\pi t)}{a^2 + (2\pi)^2}. \quad (5.7)$$

The table (1) and Figure 1 illustrate this experiment.

	Sig Trunc 1	Sig Trunc 2	Sig Trunc 3	Sig Trunc 4	Sig Trunc 5	EFM
Mean MSE	0.02356564	0.00655851	0.00374278	0.00336109	0.00330585	0.0000000

Table 1: Mean Squared Error (MSE) Comparison for Sinusoidal Seasonal Process simulation.

Figure 1: Inhomogeneous Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process with periodic mean $x_0 = 0$, $b_1 = 0.3$, $b_2 = 0.8$, $a = 1$, $\sigma = 0.9$, $\omega = 0.5$ $Q=1$.

5.1.2 Learning an Inhomogeneous Ornstein–Uhlenbeck Process with TV-EFM

We now consider an Ornstein–Uhlenbeck process whose mean-reversion speed varies periodically in 5.4. We simulate M trajectories over the interval $[0, T]$ with $T = 4$ using an Euler–Maruyama scheme with $N = 2000$ time steps. The parameters used in the simulations are

$$\kappa_0 = 1.5, \quad A = 1, \quad \theta = 0.05, \quad \sigma = 0.02, \quad \omega = 0.5.$$

We consider a fixed grid $\mathcal{T} = \{0 = t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_N = T\}$ with $N \in \mathbb{N}$, we consider a grid of $\lambda \in]0, 3]$, and perform ridge regression over a subset of grid points $\mathcal{D} \subseteq \mathcal{T}$.

To estimate the dynamics of the underlying process, we adopt a regression framework with ridge regularization. The augmented path is defined as

$$B_t = (t, W_t),$$

where W_t denotes a Brownian motion. The predictor at time t_n is given by

$$\hat{X}_{t_n} = \langle \ell, \text{TVSig}(B; f)_{0, t_n}^\lambda \rangle,$$

and the coefficient vector ℓ is estimated via ridge regression and X the corresponding solution to 5.4.

$$\hat{\ell} = \arg \min_{\ell} \frac{1}{|D|M} \sum_{i=1}^M \sum_{t_n \in D} \left(X_{t_n}^{(i)} - \langle \ell, \text{TVSig}(B^{(i)}; f)_{0, t_n}^\lambda \rangle \right)^2 + \eta \|\ell\|_2^2.$$

The performance is evaluated using the Mean Squared Error (MSE) and the coefficient of determination R^2 .

Figure 2: $\kappa_0 = 1.5$, $A = 0.8$, $\theta = 0.05$, $\sigma = 0.02$, $\omega = 2\pi K$, $K = 10$, $\text{Trunc} = 5$

Method	MSE [0,2]	R^2 [0,2]	MSE [0,4]	R^2 global [0,4]	R^2 test mean [0,4]
Classic	3.418×10^{-5}	0.749651	2.67×10^{-4}	-1.126954	-7.627587
TVSig	3.644×10^{-8}	0.999733	1.00×10^{-6}	0.991656	0.969581
EFM	4.215×10^{-8}	0.999691	3.00×10^{-6}	0.977549	0.901876

Table 2: Comparison of model performance: Signature classique (Classic), Time-Variant Signature (TVSig(t^2)), and Extended Feature Model (EFM).

5.2 Optimal Entry and Exit with TV-EFM in Statistical Arbitrage

This section investigates the use of the TV-EFM signature in the context of statistical arbitrage and optimal mean-reversion trading. Our objective is to study how this fading-memory representation can be exploited to design data-driven entry and exit strategies for mean-reverting spreads. We work in the classical pairs-trading setting, where the spread between two cointegrated assets exhibits mean-reverting dynamics. In this setting, the trading problem naturally takes the form of a sequential optimal stopping problem: one must determine when to enter a position and when to exit it in order to maximize the expected reward. Our methodology follows the signature-based optimal stopping framework developed in Ning et al. [2023], which formulates optimal timing rules as stopping policies learned from simulated trajectories. The main difference in our work is that we replace the classical signature representation with the TV-EFM signature introduced in Section 3.

5.2.1 Signature Optimal Mean Reversion Trading

Optimal stopping and statistical arbitrage. In statistical arbitrage, pairs trading strategies typically rely on the mean-reverting property of a spread process $X_t = S_t^1 - \beta S_t^2$, where S^1 and S^2 are cointegrated asset prices. The practitioner faces a sequential decision problem: given a current spread level, when to enter a position (expecting reversion) and when to exit (taking profits). This is naturally framed as an **optimal stopping problem**. For a finite horizon $T > 0$ and a measurable payoff function $\phi : \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, the value function is defined as

$$V(t, x) = \sup_{\tau \in \mathcal{T}_{t,T}} \mathbb{E}[\phi(X_\tau) \mid X_t = x], \quad (5.8)$$

where $\mathcal{T}_{t,T}$ denotes the set of all stopping times taking values in $[t, T]$. The optimal stopping time τ^* is the first time the process X exits a continuation region, which is typically unknown and must be learned from data.

Signature-based stopping policies. Solving (5.8) analytically is possible only in simple cases. For general dynamics, one resorts to approximation methods. A powerful modern approach leverages the **signature of a path**. The main idea is to approximate stopping rules through linear functionals of signatures of the time-augmented path. Let

$$\hat{X}_t = (t, X_t) \in \mathbb{R}^{d+1}$$

denote the augmented path. The truncated signature $\text{Sig}(\hat{X})_{0,t}^{\leq M}$ is used as a feature representation of the trajectory up to time t .

Following Ning et al. [2023], one introduces a linear stopping policy

$$\theta_\ell(\hat{X}_{[0,t]}) = \langle \ell, \text{Sig}(\hat{X})_{0,t}^{\leq M} \rangle, \quad \ell \in T^{(M)}((\mathbb{R}^{d+1})^*),$$

and constructs a stopping rule from this policy. In the non-randomized implementation used in practice, the stopping time is defined on a discrete grid $0 = t_0 < \dots < t_n = T$ by

$$\tau_\ell = \inf \left\{ 0 \leq j \leq n : \sum_{i=0}^j \langle \ell, \text{Sig}(\hat{X})_{0,t_i}^{\leq M} \rangle^2 \geq k \right\}, \quad (5.9)$$

where $k > 0$ is a fixed threshold parameter. This yields a deterministic approximation of the optimal stopping rule.

Training loss. The coefficient vector ℓ is learned from simulated trajectories by minimizing the signature-optimal-stopping loss introduced in Ning et al. [2023]. More precisely, given N training paths $\hat{X}^{(m)}$, $m = 1, \dots, N$, and the associated payoff processes $Y^{(m)}$, the optimized linear functional is obtained by minimizing

$$\text{loss}(\ell) = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{m=1}^N \left\{ Y_0^{(m)} + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \hat{G}_k \left(\sum_{i=0}^j \langle \ell, \text{Sig}(\hat{X}^{(m)})_{0,t_i}^{\leq M} \rangle^2 \right) (Y_{j+1}^{(m)} - Y_j^{(m)}) \right\}, \quad (5.10)$$

where $\hat{G}_k = 1 - \hat{F}_k$, and \hat{F}_k is a smooth sigmoid approximation of the indicator function centered at the threshold k .

TV-EFM formulation. The standard signature treats all past observations symmetrically. In a mean-reverting context, however, this may be suboptimal: recent deviations from equilibrium are often more informative than distant past observations. The TV-EFM signature introduced in Section 3 addresses this issue by incorporating a time-dependent fading-memory mechanism through the pair (λ, f) . For the augmented path $\hat{X}_t = (t, X_t)$, we therefore replace the classical signature features by

$$\text{TVSig}(\hat{X}; f)_{0,t}^{\lambda, \leq M}.$$

In complete analogy with the classical construction, we define the TV-EFM stopping policy

$$\theta_\ell^{\text{TV-EFM}}(\hat{X}_{[0,t]}) = \langle \ell, \text{TVSig}(\hat{X}; f)_{0,t}^{\lambda, \leq M} \rangle,$$

and the associated stopping rule

$$\tau_\ell^{\text{TV-EFM}} = \inf \left\{ 0 \leq j \leq n : \sum_{i=0}^j \langle \ell, \text{TVSig}(\hat{X}; f)_{0,t_i}^{\lambda, \leq M} \rangle^2 \geq k \right\}. \quad (5.11)$$

The corresponding training problem becomes

$$\text{loss}_{\text{TV-EFM}}(\ell) = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{m=1}^N \left\{ Y_0^{(m)} + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \hat{G}_k \left(\sum_{i=0}^j \langle \ell, \text{TVSig}(\hat{X}^{(m)}; f)_{0,t_i}^{\lambda, \leq M} \rangle^2 \right) (Y_{j+1}^{(m)} - Y_j^{(m)}) \right\}. \quad (5.12)$$

Thus, our contribution in this section is not to modify the optimal stopping framework itself, but rather to replace the path representation used in the stopping policy and the loss function. In other words, we keep the methodology of Ning et al. [2023] and substitute the classical signature with the stationary TV-EFM signature.

Objectives of the numerical study. Our empirical investigation, detailed in the following subsections, pursues two main goals. First, we benchmark the performance of the EFM-type representation against the classical signature in solving optimal stopping problems for Ornstein–Uhlenbeck processes, which constitute the canonical model for mean-reverting spreads. Second, we illustrate the practical relevance of the resulting stopping rules by displaying explicit entry and exit signals on simulated trajectories. The experimental setup therefore follows the methodology of Ning et al. [2023], while replacing the feature representation by the TV-EFM signature whenever fading memory is introduced.

5.2.2 Experiments on Simulated Data

In this section, we conduct simulated experiments to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed signature-based optimal mean-reversion trading method.

Test on signature and EFM optimal stopping method. In this section, we perform simulations to assess the effectiveness of the optimal stopping method based on classical signatures and EFM signatures in the context of mean-reverting spreads. We use the Ornstein–Uhlenbeck (OU) process to model a mean-reverting spread, governed by the following stochastic differential equation :

$$dX_t = \theta(\mu - X_t) dt + \sigma dW_t. \tag{5.13}$$

Our main objective is to identify an upper bound for the expected value of the OU process at the optimal stopping time based on the signature representation, formally defined as

$$\sup_{\tau \in \mathcal{S}} \mathbb{E}[X_{\tau \wedge T}].$$

The application of the signature-based optimal stopping method to the OU process follows a two-step procedure. First, we generate a set of 200 simulated trajectories, which are used as training data. From these trajectories, we estimate the optimal linear functional l^* by minimizing the loss function defined in Equation (19), for both approaches considered: the classical signature and the EFM signature. This stage corresponds to the training phase of the model and allows us to calibrate the optimal stopping criterion. The results obtained are summarized in Table 3. We observe that, for all configurations considered, both methods produce stopping values greater than the long-term mean $\mu = 0.2$, which confirms the relevance of the methodological framework. However, the EFM signature consistently achieves better performance than the classical signature. This improvement can be explained by the explicit incorporation of the stationary structure of the process, allowing a more accurate capture of the underlying dynamics. Figure 3 illustrates a representative example corresponding to the parameters $\mu = 0.2$, $\sigma = 2$, and $\theta = 10$. The simulated trajectories and the stopping times estimated by the two methods, based on the optimal vector l^* learned during the training phase, are displayed. Visually, the stopping times obtained using the EFM signature are on average closer to the trajectory maxima than those obtained using the classical signature, confirming the quantitative results reported in the comparison table.

Overall, these results highlight the effectiveness of the EFM approach in a stationary mean-reverting setting and emphasize the importance of explicitly incorporating the dynamic structure of the process when constructing signatures for optimal stopping problems.

θ	σ	μ	Sig	EFM
1	1.0	0.2	0.046 431	1.283776
5	1.0	0.2	0.523 433	0.886507
10	1.0	0.2	0.460 702	0.700590
12	1.0	0.2	0.350 060	0.658752
20	1.0	0.2	0.373 721	0.559442
10	0.5	0.2	0.295 901	0.450295
10	1.5	0.2	0.346 142	0.950885
10	2.0	0.2	0.460 791	1.201180

Table 3: Optimal stopping values computed using classical signatures and EFM signatures for different parameter configurations ($\mu = 0.2$).

Figure 3: Simulated trajectories and optimal stopping values computed for $\mu = 0.2$, $\sigma = 2$, and $\theta = 10$.

Simulation on EFM-Signature Optimal Mean-Reversion Trading. In this section, we focus exclusively on the **EFM signature**. We design a simulation framework based on the Ornstein–Uhlenbeck (OU) process in order to evaluate the performance of our method for determining optimal trading times. The objective is to analyze its ability to effectively identify entry and exit points in a market environment characterized by mean-reverting dynamics. The trajectories are generated using the OU model, which reproduces the stochastic behavior typically observed in mean-reverting assets. This numerical study aims to assess the practical relevance of our approach for decision-making based on the dynamics of the underlying stochastic process. Figure 4 presents the results obtained from the simulations. The entry times detected by the algorithm are indicated by **circles**, while the exit times are represented by **crosses**. This visualization allows an immediate interpretation of the decisions produced by the method and highlights its ability to identify opportunities consistent with the natural movements of the process. Inspection of the figure shows that the generated signals generally coincide with turning points of the process, particularly near local maxima and minima. This observation suggests that

the algorithm effectively captures the mean-reversion structure inherent in the **OU process**. The results therefore provide strong empirical support for the theoretical analysis developed previously. More generally, these simulations underline the robustness and practical relevance of our approach. They show that the algorithm is capable of producing coherent and actionable trading signals based on the dynamic properties of the stochastic process, making it a potentially valuable tool for active management and the implementation of mean-reversion trading strategies.

Figure 4: Sequential optimal entry and exit times for a simulated mean-reversion process based on the optimal trade timing framework, with $\mu = 10$, $\theta = 10$, and $\sigma = 1$.

6. PROOF OF PROPOSITION 3.6

Let $t = (t_1, t_2)$.

The properties (1)–(4) follow immediately from the definition.

For (5), recall that

$$(p \otimes q)^v = \sum_{\substack{u, w \\ uw=v}} p^u q^w.$$

So that

$$\left(\Phi_t^{\lambda, f}(p \otimes q) \right)^v = e^{-\lambda^v F_{t_1, t_2}} \sum_{\substack{u, w \\ uw=v}} p^u q^w.$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\Phi_t^{\lambda, f}(p \otimes q) \right)^v &= \sum_{\substack{u, w \\ uw=v}} \left(e^{-\lambda^u F_{t_1, t_2}} p^u \right) \left(e^{-\lambda^w F_{t_1, t_2}} q^w \right) \\ &= \left(\Phi_t^{\lambda, f} p \otimes \Phi_t^{\lambda, f} q \right)^v, \end{aligned}$$

since

$$\lambda^v = \lambda^u + \lambda^w \quad \text{for all } u, w \text{ such that } uw = v.$$

For (6), similarly

$$\left(\Lambda_{f(t_1)}(p \otimes q) \right)^v = \lambda^v f(t_1) \sum_{\substack{u, w \\ uw=v}} p^u q^w.$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\Lambda_{f(t_1)}(p \otimes q) \right)^v &= f(t_1) \sum_{\substack{u, w \\ uw=v}} (\lambda^u p^u q^w + \lambda^w p^u q^w) \\ &= f(t_1) \sum_{\substack{u, w \\ uw=v}} ((\lambda^u p^u) q^w + p^u (\lambda^w q^w)). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore

$$\left(\Lambda_{f(t_1)}(p \otimes q) \right)^v = \left(\Lambda_{f(t_1)} p \otimes q \right)^v + \left(p \otimes \Lambda_{f(t_1)} q \right)^v.$$

Hence

$$\Lambda_{f(t_1)}(p \otimes q) = (\Lambda_{f(t_1)} p) \otimes q + p \otimes (\Lambda_{f(t_1)} q).$$

7. PROOF OF PROPOSITION 4.2

We consider the truncated signature transform

$$\text{TVSig}(X, f)_{s, t}^{k, \lambda}.$$

By definition,

$$\text{TVSig}(X, f)_{s, t}^{k, \lambda} = \int_{s < u_1 < \dots < u_k < t} e^{-\lambda F_{u_1, t}} \circ dX_{u_1} \otimes \dots \otimes e^{-\lambda F_{u_k, t}} \circ dX_{u_k}.$$

Expanding the integral we obtain

$$= \sum_{i=1}^k \int e^{-F_{u_1,t}} \circ dX_{u_1} \otimes \cdots \otimes e^{-F_{u_k,t}} \circ dX_{u_k}.$$

Using the decomposition

$$F_{u_i,t} = F_{u_i,\ell} + F_{\ell,t},$$

we rewrite

$$e^{-F_{u_i,t}} = e^{-F_{u_i,\ell}} e^{-F_{\ell,t}}.$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \text{TVSig}(X, f)_{s,t}^{k,\lambda} &= \sum_{i=1}^k e^{-\lambda F_{\ell,t}} \left(\int_{s < u_1 < \cdots < u_i < \ell} e^{-\lambda F_{u_1,\ell}} \circ dX_{u_1} \otimes \cdots \otimes e^{-\lambda F_{u_i,\ell}} \circ dX_{u_i} \right) \\ &\otimes \left(\int_{\ell < u_{i+1} < \cdots < u_k < t} e^{-\lambda F_{u_{i+1},t}} \circ dX_{u_{i+1}} \otimes \cdots \otimes e^{-\lambda F_{u_k,t}} \circ dX_{u_k} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Recognizing the truncated signature terms gives

$$= \sum_{i=1}^k \Phi_{\ell,t}^{\lambda} \left(\text{TVSig}(X, f)_{s,\ell}^{i,\lambda} \right) \otimes \text{TVSig}(X, f)_{\ell,t}^{k-i,\lambda}.$$

Therefore

$$\text{TVSig}(X, f)_{s,t}^{k,\lambda} = \sum_{i=1}^k \Phi_{\ell,t}^{\lambda} \left(\text{TVSig}(X, f)_{s,\ell}^{i,\lambda} \right) \otimes \text{TVSig}(X, f)_{\ell,t}^{k-i,\lambda}.$$

In particular,

$$\text{TVSig}(X, f)_{s,t}^{\lambda} = \Phi_{\ell,t}^{\lambda} \left(\text{TVSig}(X, f)_{s,\ell}^{\lambda} \right) \otimes \text{TVSig}(X, f)_{\ell,t}^{\lambda}.$$

8. PROOF OF 4.2

Let X be a linear path on $[a, b]$, i.e.

$$X_t = X_a + \frac{t-a}{b-a} (X_b - X_a), \quad t \in [a, b].$$

For the k -th term we have

$$\text{TVSig}(X, f)_{s,t}^{k,\lambda} = \int_{s < u_1 < \cdots < u_k < t} e^{-\lambda F_{u_1,t}} \circ dX_{u_1} \otimes \cdots \otimes e^{-\lambda F_{u_k,t}} \circ dX_{u_k}.$$

Since X is linear,

$$dX_u = \frac{X_b - X_a}{b-a} du.$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \text{TVSig}(X, f)_{s,t}^{k,\lambda} &= \int_{s < u_1 < \cdots < u_k < t} e^{-\lambda F_{u_1,t}} \frac{X_b - X_a}{b-a} du_1 \otimes \cdots \otimes e^{-\lambda F_{u_k,t}} \frac{X_b - X_a}{b-a} du_k \\ &= \frac{(X_b - X_a)^{\otimes k}}{(b-a)^k} \int_{s < u_1 < \cdots < u_k < t} e^{-\lambda F_{u_1,t}} \cdots e^{-\lambda F_{u_k,t}} du_1 \cdots du_k. \end{aligned}$$

Using the symmetry of the simplex integral we obtain

$$\text{TVSig}(X, f)_{s,t}^{k,\lambda} = \frac{1}{k!} \left(\frac{X_b - X_a}{b - a} \int_s^t e^{-\lambda F_{u,t}} du \right)^{\otimes k}.$$

Summing over k gives the tensor exponential

$$\text{TVSig}(X, f)_{s,t}^\lambda = \sum_{k \geq 0} \frac{1}{k!} \left(\frac{X_b - X_a}{b - a} \int_s^t e^{-\lambda F_{u,t}} du \right)^{\otimes k}.$$

Therefore

$$\text{TVSig}(X, f)_{s,t}^\lambda = \exp^{\otimes} \left(\frac{X_b - X_a}{b - a} \int_s^t e^{-\lambda F_{u,t}} du \right).$$

Finally, combining this expression with the Chen identity (Proposition 4.1) yields equation (4.2).

9. PROOF OF PROPOSITION 4.4

We start from

$$d \text{TVSig}^{\mu,\lambda} = -f(t) \lambda^\mu \text{TVSig}^{\mu,\lambda} dt + \text{TVSig}^{\tilde{\mu},\lambda} \circ dX^i, \quad (a)$$

and

$$d \text{TVSig}^{\nu,\lambda} = -f(t) \lambda^\nu \text{TVSig}^{\nu,\lambda} dt + \text{TVSig}^{\tilde{\nu},\lambda} \circ dX^j, \quad (b)$$

where

$$\mu = \tilde{\mu} i, \quad \nu = \tilde{\nu} j.$$

Applying the product rule, we obtain

$$d(\text{TVSig}^{\mu,\lambda} \text{TVSig}^{\nu,\lambda}) = (d \text{TVSig}^{\mu,\lambda}) \text{TVSig}^{\nu,\lambda} + \text{TVSig}^{\mu,\lambda} (d \text{TVSig}^{\nu,\lambda}).$$

Substituting (a) and (b) gives

$$\begin{aligned} d(\text{TVSig}^{\mu,\lambda} \text{TVSig}^{\nu,\lambda}) &= \left(-f(t) \lambda^\mu \text{TVSig}^{\mu,\lambda} dt + \text{TVSig}^{\tilde{\mu},\lambda} \circ dX^i \right) \text{TVSig}^{\nu,\lambda} \\ &\quad + \text{TVSig}^{\mu,\lambda} \left(-f(t) \lambda^\nu \text{TVSig}^{\nu,\lambda} dt + \text{TVSig}^{\tilde{\nu},\lambda} \circ dX^j \right). \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} d(\text{TVSig}^{\mu,\lambda} \text{TVSig}^{\nu,\lambda}) &= -f(t) (\lambda^\mu + \lambda^\nu) \text{TVSig}^{\mu,\lambda} \text{TVSig}^{\nu,\lambda} dt \\ &\quad + \text{TVSig}^{\tilde{\mu},\lambda} \text{TVSig}^{\nu,\lambda} \circ dX^i + \text{TVSig}^{\tilde{\nu},\lambda} \text{TVSig}^{\mu,\lambda} \circ dX^j. \end{aligned}$$

Integrating, we get

$$\text{TVSig}^{\mu,\lambda} \text{TVSig}^{\nu,\lambda} = \int_s^t e^{-(\lambda^\mu + \lambda^\nu) F_{u,t}} \left[\text{TVSig}_u^{\tilde{\mu},\lambda} \text{TVSig}_u^{\nu,\lambda} \circ dX_u^i + \text{TVSig}_u^{\tilde{\nu},\lambda} \text{TVSig}_u^{\mu,\lambda} \circ dX_u^j \right].$$

Equivalently,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{TVSig}^{\mu,\lambda} \text{TVSig}^{\nu,\lambda} &= \int_s^t e^{-(\lambda^\mu + \lambda^\nu) F_{u,t}} \text{TVSig} V_u^{\tilde{\mu} \sqcup \nu, \lambda} \circ dX_u^i \\ &\quad + \int_s^t e^{-(\lambda^\mu + \lambda^\nu) F_{u,t}} \text{TVSig} V_u^{\tilde{\nu} \sqcup \mu, \lambda} \circ dX_u^j. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\text{TVSig}^{\mu,\lambda} \text{TVSig}^{\nu,\lambda} = \text{TVSig}^{\mu \sqcup \nu, \lambda},$$

which concludes the proof.

10. PROOF OF PROPOSITION 4.6

Write

$$\ell = \sum_{m \geq 0} \sum_{|v|=m}^v \ell^v v.$$

Then

$$\langle \ell_t, \text{TVSig}(X)_t \rangle = \sum_{m \geq 0} \sum_{|v|=m}^v \ell_t^v \text{TVSig}(X)_t^v.$$

Applying the product rule gives

$$d\langle \ell_t, \text{TVSig}(X)_t \rangle = \sum_{m \geq 0} \sum_{|v|=m}^v d(\ell_t^v \text{TVSig}(X)_t^v) = \sum_{m \geq 0} \sum_{|v|=m}^v \dot{\ell}_t^v \text{TVSig}(X)_t^v dt + \sum_{m \geq 0} \sum_{|v|=m}^v \ell_t^v d\text{TVSig}(X)_t^v.$$

Using the dynamics of $\text{TVSig}(X)_t^v$ from Proposition 3.8, we obtain the desired formula. This concludes the proof. \square

11. PROOF OF PROPOSITION 4.7

By applying (4.9), we obtain

$$d\langle \ell_t, \text{TVSig}(X) \rangle = \left\langle \dot{\ell}_t - \Lambda_{f(t)} \ell_t, \text{TVSig}(X) \right\rangle dt + \sum_{i=1}^d \langle \ell_t | i, \text{TVSig}(X) \rangle \circ dX_t^i.$$

Set

$$a := \sum_{i=1}^d \langle \ell_t | i, \text{TVSig}(X) \rangle \circ dX_t^i.$$

Then

$$a = \sum_{i=1}^d \langle \ell_t | i, \text{TVSig}(X) \rangle \circ dX_t^i.$$

Passing from Stratonovich to Itô form,

$$a = \sum_{i=1}^d \langle \ell_t | i, \text{TVSig}(X) \rangle dX_t^i + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^d d \langle \ell_t | i, \text{TVSig}(X) \rangle dX_t^i.$$

Using again formula (4.9) on $\langle \ell_t | i, TV \rangle$, this yields

$$a = \sum_{i=1}^d \langle \ell_t | i, \text{TVSig}(X) \rangle dX_t^i + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^d \sum_{j \in A_d} \langle \ell_t | ij, \text{TVSig}(X) \rangle d\langle X^j, X^i \rangle_t.$$

Therefore,

$$d\langle \ell_t, \text{TVSig}(X) \rangle = \langle \dot{\ell}_t - \Lambda_{f(t)} \ell_t, \text{TVSig}(X) \rangle dt + \sum_{i=1}^d \langle \ell_t | i, \text{TVSig}(X) \rangle dX_t^i + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^d \sum_{j \in A_d} \langle \ell_t | ij, \text{TVSig}(X) \rangle d\langle X^j, X^i \rangle_t.$$

This is the announced result. □

It is easily shown that :

$$\left\langle \frac{\Re((b_2 - i\omega)e^{\perp\perp i\omega 1}) - e^{\perp\perp -b_2 1}}{b^2 + \omega^2}, \text{TVSig}_t^{\lambda,1}(X) \right\rangle = \mu_2 b_1 \int_0^t e^{-b_2(t-s)} \cos(\omega s) ds$$

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